

Influence of Study Habits on Academic Performance of Business Education Students in Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano

Umar, Zango Abdulkadir

Email: abdulkadir4rl@gmail.com

Tel: +2348029805463

Department of Business Education, School of Vocational and Technical Education
Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso

Abstract

The study examines the influence of study habits on academic performance of Business Education students in Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano. Three research objectives, research questions and Corresponding hypotheses, respectively guided the study. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was one thousand and sixty-six of Business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano State during the 2022/2023 academic session. Sample size of 474 (Male 275 & Female 199) students were selected using the Research Advisor's table. Instrument used to collect data for this study is the structured questionnaire. The instrument was vetted by three experts in the field of business education. The reliability of the instrument was established using pilot-test and calculation of data using Cronbach method yielded correlation coefficient of 0.725. Regression analysis was used to analyze the data at 0.05 level of significance. The study found among others significant influence of study habits on academic performance of Business Education students. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that business education students should be encouraged on the need to be jotting down important point during teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Business Education Programme, Note taking, Reading Habit, Use of library.

Introduction

According to Suleman and Akaeze (2014) Business education is an aspect of total educational programme which provides the recipients with knowledge, skills, understanding and attitudes needed to perform well in business world as a producer, entrepreneur or consumer of goods and services. Business education is a programme of study that trained the participant to acquire skills, which will lead its students to fit into the field of work. Auwal and Abdulkadir (2020) viewed business education as a discipline or programme of study that equips the students with two functional skills. The functional skills are as follows: office work and teaching skills in order to learn and solve his or her societal problems. Adeshina (2017) sees business education as a training system that encourage the beneficiary to acquire skills into the world of work. He further goes ahead that business education encompasses with attitude, knowledge and skills needed by all citizens in order to function effectively in managing their personal business and economic system. Osuala (2004) in Abdulkadir (2020) defines Business Education as a programme of instruction which consists of two parts (1) Office education – a vocational programme of office careers through initial, refresher and upgrading education and (2) General business education – a programme to provide students with information and competences which are needed by all in managing personal business affairs and in using the services of the business.

According to Asomeji and Amadi (2022) academic performance is the accomplishment or acquired proficiency in the performance of an individual in a given skill or body of knowledge. Academic performance means —knowledge attained and skill developed in the school subjects usually designated by test scores or by marks assigned by teachers or by both. At the university level of education, students' academic performance in any semester is measured with the grade point average (G.P.A). Cumulative Grade Point Average is the measure of the students overall academic performance at any given point in his programme. (GPA is an up-to-date weighted mean of the grade points, where the weights are the course credit units. Academic performance refers to the act that shows how well students prepared, organised, gathered and acquired on subjects through examinations or tests which were given to them by the lectures and performed better and mastered on all the materials given to the students by their Business Education lecturers for the achievement of stated goals.

Note taking is an essential learning skill for college students to implement during and outside of class time. The notes recorded during a class lecture should be compiled of the important facts or ideas presented by the lecturers. Implementing a system of note taking is important for several reasons. First, the faculty member may be presenting supplemental material not

Influence of Study Habits on Academic ... (Umar, Z. A. 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8384635>

found in your text book but critical for you to learn in order to make a connection to prior knowledge or introduce new material within your textbook. A system of good note taking is an important study strategy. Actively listening and taking notes during class increases the retention of the material. Reviewing the notes immediately after class to add additional points or to generate questions for clarification creates opportunity for additional retention and understanding. Effective note taking skills will assist in preparing for exams and future knowledge base of material. Note taking is an effective strategy for students because it helps the brain encode learned information. Luo et al. (2018) notes do need to be written down to have an impact on the encoding process. They further stated that hearing and writing lesson material is better than simply hearing it because additional writing leads to more distinctive encoding and better memory for the lesson material. Dewey (2021) added to this idea by explaining that students who took more notes performed significantly better on a recall test. Williams (2015) also investigated note taking trends in regard to the total amount of words recorded, as well as the relevance of those words. Results indicated that taking notes during a lecture was beneficial to academic performance because students were able to record more relevant information. Reading habit refers to the behaviour which expresses the likeness of reading of individual types of reading and tastes of reading. It means that someone who has behaviour spending time to read anything. Reading can be said habit because it is repetition action and become something routinely did. Besides, Reading is one of the effective ways to be a good reader, good speller, advanced grammatical competence, reliable writer, and mastered vocabulary. It can refer that learners who have good reading habit, they can increase their acquisition in grammar then good in writing. Students reading habit is defined as the frequency, duration, and type of reading that students engage in. It is a complex behavior that is influenced by a variety of factors, including student motivation, interest, and access to reading materials. This is in line with Quinn et al (2014) that stated the improvement of reading comprehension depends on the vocabulary knowledge. Many researchers agree that through reading student can increase their vocabulary knowledge which is very useful in acquiring other skills in language learning. Therefore, it is very essential for student to improve their reading skill.

Library use is defined as the extent to which students utilize library resources, such as books, articles, databases, and other materials, for their academic studies. This includes both the physical use of libraries, such as visiting the library and borrowing materials, and the virtual use of libraries, such as accessing library resources online (Foster and Gibbons 2019). Kuhlthau, *et al* (2015) opined that Library use and academic performance are interrelated concepts. The use of libraries can support academic performance by providing students with access to a variety of resources, such as books, articles, databases, and other materials. Libraries can also provide students with a quiet place to study and to collaborate with other students. Additionally, libraries can provide students with access to librarians, who can help them to find the information they need and to develop their research skills. The main problem of this study is to assess the relationship between reading habit, note-taking and use of library and academic performance business education students in Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kano State.

There are serious complains by the parents and general public over the falling standard of educational system and the poor academic performance of Business education students, Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kano State. This is deeply rooted right from the primary education and external examinations conducting by National Examination Council (NECO), West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) and University Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) and others external examination. The situation drawn the attention of educationists and other stakeholder and tend to shift the blame on the teachers and their teaching methodology adopted by them as well as the insufficient funding by the government to provide adequate instructional materials and functional e- libraries. Study habit contribute to the incessant failure of business education students in just concluded 2022/2023 academic session examination. As a result of poor study habit among students, the issue of examinations malpractice, failure, school drop- out etc. are on the increase. Therefore, the main problem of this study is to assess the relationship between reading habit, note-taking and use of library and academic performance business education of students, Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kano State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to assess the impact of study habits on academic Performance of business education students in Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kano State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Assess relationship between reading habit and academic performance among business education students in Saadatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano.
2. Assess relationship between note taking and academic performance among business education students in Saadatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano.
3. Assess relationship between use of library and academic performance among business education students in Saadatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano

Influence of Study Habits on Academic ... (Umar, Z. A. 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8384635>

Research Questions:

1. What is the relationship between reading habit and academic performance among business education students in Saadatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano?
2. What is the relationship between note-taking and academic performance among business education students in Saadatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano?
3. What is the relationship between use of library and academic performance among business education students in Saadatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between students reading habit and academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.
2. There is no significant difference between note-taking and academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.
3. There is no significant difference between use of library and academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.

Methodology

The study adopted correlational research design to measure the relationship between the study habits and academic performance among NCE business education students of Saadatu Rimi College of education, Kano. The population of the study was one thousand and sixty-six of Buisness education students of Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano State during the 2022/2023 academic session. Sample size of 474 (Male 275 & Female 199) students were selected using research advisor’s table. Instrument used to collect data for this study is the structured questionnaire. The instrument was vetted by three experts in the field of business education. The reliability of the instrument was established using pilot-test and calculation of data using Crombach method yielded correlation coefficient of 0.725. The questionnaire was divided into two sections (A and B); section “A” contains bio-data of the respondents while section “B” consisted of 24 questionnaire items. The questionnaire was administered by the researcher to the business education students with an explanation on how to fill it. The researcher used descriptive and correlation statistics in analysis of the data. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Mean rating below 2.5 was rejected while any rating of 2.5 and above was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between reading habit and academic performance among business education students in Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano?

Table 2: Mean Score of Respondents on Reading Habit and Academic Performance

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision	
1	I find it difficult while reading my note book	2.80	0.70	Agreed	
2	I find it interesting if I am reading my note book	2.82	0.66	Agreed	
3	If I am reading my note book I find it boring	2.81	0.73	Agreed	
4	It is rewarding reading my note book		2.81	0.72	Agreed
5	I enjoy reading my note books	2.82	0.70	Agreed	
Cumulative mean		2.81	0.70	Agreed	

(Field Study, 2023)

The analysis of item 1-5 used to answer research question one was presented in table 2 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean value found to be greater than the index score for agree (2.81>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.70. The analysis therefore indicated that reading habit influence the academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano.

Influence of Study Habits on Academic ... (Umar, Z. A. 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8384635>

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between note-taking and academic performance among business education students in saadatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano?

Table 3: Mean score of respondents on note -taking and academic performance.

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
6	I used to listen attentively while taking down notes in The class.	2.80	0.70	Agreed
7	I always pay attention in the class in order to take any important notes.	2.82	0.66	Agreed
8	I have developed skills for effective note taking during every lesson.	2.81	0.73	Agreed
9	I always take down note to preserve new knowledge.	2.81	0.72	Agreed
10	Most times, I use symbols to express what my teacher say in the class	2.80	0.70	Agreed
Cumulative mean		2.81	0.70	Agreed

(Field Study, 2023)

The analysis of item 6-10 used to answer research question two was presented in table 3 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean value found to be greater than the index score for agree (2.81>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.70. The result was concluded that note- taking influence the academic performance of business education students, Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano.

Research Question 3

What is the relationship between use of library and academic performance among business education students in saadatu Rimi College of Education Kumbotso, Kano?

Table 4: Mean score of respondents on use of library and academic performance

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
11	I have devoted my interest in library resources utilization.	2.82	0.73	Agreed
12	I study in the library every day.	2.82	0.72	Agreed
13	I used to do my assignment in the school library.	2.82	0.72	Agreed
14	My school library gives me access to variety of resources.	2.82	0.72	Agreed
15	I make use of the library to expand the scope of my study	2.81	0.72	Agreed
Cumulative mean		2.80	0.72	Agreed

(Field Study, 2023)

The analysis of item 11-15 used to answer research question two was presented in table 3 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean value found to be greater than the index score for agree (2.81>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.70. The result was concluded that notes taking influence the academic performance of business education students, Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant influence of reading habit on academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.

Table 5: Regression Analysis on influence of Reading Habit and the academic performance among NCE Business Education students Sa’adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sign
Reading Habit	1.654	0.078	21.247	0.607	0.369	0.367	0.000
(Constant)							
Academic performance	0.421	0.025					

Influence of Study Habits on Academic ... (Umar, Z. A. 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8384635>

The regression analysis on table 5 was to determine how reading habit influence the academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi Collage of Education, kumbotso Kano. The result revealed a constant Beta value (Reading Habit) of 1.654 with the t-value of 21.247 against the coefficient value of 0.421 (academic performance). The r-value was 0.607 with r^2 - value of 0.369 and adjusted-r of 0.369 with a p-value of 0.000. The result indicated that, reading habit had a variance at 36% ($r^2 0.369 \times 100$). This means that for any increase in reading habit, there was an increase in students' academic performance. The observed $P = 0.000$ was less than α value (0.05) indicating a significant influence. This implies that reading habit had a significant influence on academic performance among NCE business education students of sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of note-taking on academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.

Table 6: Regression Analysis on influence of Notes Taking and the academic performance among NCE Business Education students of Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sign	
Notes Taking (Constant)		1.225	0.113	10.826	0.569	0.324	0.323	0.000
Academic performance	0.590	0.039						

P<.05

The regression analysis on table 6 was to determine how reading habit influence the academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi Collage of Education, kumbotso Kano. The result revealed a constant Beta value (Notes Taking) of 1.225 with the t-value of 10.826 against the coefficient value of 0.590 (academic performance). The r-value was 0.569 with r^2 - value of 0.324 and adjusted-r of 0.323 with a p-value of 0.000. The result indicated that, notes taking had a variance at 32% ($r^2 0.324 \times 100$). This means that for any increase in notes taking, there was an increase in students' academic performance. The observed $P = 0.000$ was less than α value (0.05) indicating a significant influence. This implies that notes taking had a significant influence on academic performance among NCE business education students of sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between use of library and academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.

Table 7: Regression Analysis on influence of use of library and the academic performance among NCE Business Education students Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sign	
Use of Library (Constant)		1.927	0.114	16.909	0.371	0.138	0.136	0.000
Academic performance	0.340	0.039						

P<.05

The regression analysis on table 7 was to determine how reading habit influence the academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi Collage of Education, kumbotso Kano. The result revealed a constant Beta value (Use of Library) of 1.927 with the t-value of 16.909 against the coefficient value of 0.340 (academic performance). The r-value was 0.371 with r^2 - value of 0.138 and adjusted-r of 0.136 with a p-value of 0.000. The result indicated that, reading habit had a variance at 13.8% ($r^2 0.138 \times 100$). This means that for any increase in use of library, there was an increase in students' academic performance. The observed $P = 0.000$ was less than α value (0.05) indicating a significant influence. This implies that use of library had a significant influence on academic performance among NCE business education students of sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The finding in Table 5 related to null hypothesis one revealed that, reading habit had a variance at 36% ($r^2 0.369 \times 100$). This means that for any increase in reading habit, there was an increase in students' academic performance. The observed $P = 0.000$ was less than α value (0.05) indicating a significant influence. This implies that reading habit had a significant influence on academic performance among NCE business education students of sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano. This finding is in line with study of Ibrahim (2020) found that reading habits have a significant impact on the academic performance of NCE Business Education students. The study also found that students with good reading habits tend to have higher academic performance than students with poor reading habits.

The finding in Table 6 related to null hypothesis two revealed that, notes taking had a variance at 32% ($r^2 0.324 \times 100$). This means that for any increase in notes taking, there was an increase in students' academic performance. The observed $P = 0.000$ was less than α value (0.05) indicating a significant influence. This implies that notes taking had a significant influence on academic performance among NCE business education students of sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano. This result agrees with study done by Dewey (2021) who reported that students who took more notes performed significantly better on a recall test. Williams (2015) also investigated note taking trends in regard to the total amount of words recorded, as well as the relevance of those words. Results indicated that taking notes during a lecture was beneficial to academic performance because students were able to record more relevant information.

The finding in Table 6 related to null hypothesis three revealed that, reading habit had a variance at 13.8% ($r^2 0.138 \times 100$). This means that for any increase in use of library, there was an increase in students' academic performance. The observed $P = 0.000$ was less than α value (0.05) indicating a significant influence. This implies that use of library had a significant influence on academic performance among NCE business education students of sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso Kano. This result is in line with studies of Kuhlthau, *et al* (2015) opined that Library use and academic performance are interrelated concepts. The use of libraries can support academic performance by providing students with access to a variety of resources, such as books, articles, databases, and other materials. Libraries can also provide students with a quiet place to study and to collaborate with other students. Additionally, libraries can provide students with access to librarians, who can help them to find the information they need and to develop their research skills.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the research work, the following conclusions were drawn: Reading habit influence the academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano. This implies any increase in reading habit, there was an increase in students' academic performance. Note-taking influence the student's academic performance among NCE business education of Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano. This indicated that students who are taking notes during their lecture classes tends to perform better than the other once whose don't care to jot down what discussed during lectures classes. The result was concluded that notes taking influence the student academic performance among NCE business education. The result was also concluded that notes taking influence the academic performance among NCE business education students of Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano. This means that for any increase in use of library, there was an increase in students' academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The business education students should be encouraged on jotting down the important point discuss during the lecture classes. By doing so, it will lead to increase of their academic performance.
2. Schools and colleges should provide functional e-libraries, this would encourage the students to develop good study habit and also increases their academic performance.
3. The lectures should encourage students to be forming group discussions after the lecture classes, this will lead to their good academic performance.
4. Parents/ guardians should be checking their wards reading materials to make sure they are jotting down lecture notes.

Acknowledgements

This research work will not forget the efforts made by the entire Business Education Department's staff, Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano especially the Head of Department, level coordinators and students, may almighty reward you

Influence of Study Habits on Academic ... (Umar, Z. A. 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8384635>

all. Malam Auwalu Said Mahmoud and Malam Mustapha Zakariyya, I am very grateful and your efforts are highly appreciated. Thank you all.

References

- Abdel Abdulkadir, U. Z. (2020). New technology in business education in Nigeria: issues and trends. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 7(1):134-142.
- Adeshina, T. J. (2017). *Understanding Business Education*. Esonaj Publishers Sabon Gari Zaria.
- Asomeji, D. and Dr. Amadi K. (2022). Influence of Time Management on academic performance of Business Education Students in Universities in Rivers State. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 3(6):2793-2798.
- Auwal, S. M. and Zango, U. A. (2020). Influence of supervision of business education and sustainable development of students in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Nigeria. *Delta Business Education Journal (DBEJ)*, 10(1):163-170.
- Dewey, A. M. (2021). *An evaluation of interspersing the testing effect during lecture on test performance and notes in high scholars [ProQuest Information & Learning]*. In Dissertation Abstracts International Section A: Humanities and Social Sciences (Vol. 82, Issue 3–A).
- Gidado, S. D., & Akaeze, P. (2014). Role of business education in promoting entrepreneurship in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 3(4), 72-77
- Haynes, J. M., McCarley, N. G., & Williams, J. L. (2015). An analysis of notes taken during and after a lecture presentation. *North American Journal of Psychology*, 17(1), 175–186.
- Kuhlthau, C. C., Maniotes, L., & Caspari, A. (2015). *Guided inquiry: Learning in the 21st century* (3rd Ed.). Santa Barbara, CA: Libraries Unlimited.
- Luo, L., Kiewra, K. A., Flanigan, A. E., & Peteranetz, M. S. (2018). Laptop versus longhand note taking: Effects on lecture notes and achievement. *Instructional Science*, 46(6), 947–971.
- Quinn, J. M., Wagner, R. K., Petscher, Y., & Lopez, D. (2014). Developmental relations between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension: *A latent change score modeling study*. *Child Development*, 1–17.